

THE INFLUENCE OF TEACHERS ON SOCIAL MEDIA: PROBLEMS AND REMEDIES

*Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, Faculty of Pedagogy
Bexruzjon Valiyev Alijon o'g'li*

Abstract: *This article provides an in-depth discussion of the role of teachers in social media activities. Additionally, it highlights the invisible yet crucial issues faced by 99% of educators in our country today, which are closely tied to the future of the younger generation.*

Keywords: *Pedagogy, psychology, social activity, isolation, research, education, method, technology, internet, social media.*

In the global education system, special attention is given to ensuring quality education throughout students' lives, fostering leadership skills in society, and actively engaging them in cognitive processes through the comprehensive use of technology. The concept adopted at the World Forum on Education Problems emphasizes the importance of creating a learning environment that promotes "analysis, problem-solving, and the development of high-level cognitive, interpersonal, and social skills." This, in turn, necessitates the implementation of various models and technologies to cultivate talented youth who are holistically developed, independent thinkers, creative, socially active, intelligent, and capable of making bold strides toward a bright future. As our country is rapidly advancing, the role of social networks in daily life is expanding. This has become a natural process in modern society. The most effective way of shaping an individual's information culture is through the education system, where students and teachers are the primary objects and subjects. The term "social network" was introduced by sociologist James Barnes in 1954. At that time, it had no connection to the internet and was defined as "a social structure consisting of nodes (people and organizations) that act as social objects and the connections (social relationships) between them." Simply put, a social network is a group of people who exchange information and have one-way or two-way connections. Examples include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Telegram, Google, TikTok, Pinterest, Snapchat, YouTube, Reddit, WhatsApp, Flickr, and Weibo.

Excessive use of these networks can lead to the "isolation" of children. Research published in the "American Journal of Preventive Medicine" suggests that social media does not alleviate feelings of loneliness or a lack of communication but rather intensifies them. Researchers have found that social isolation is associated with high mortality rates among young people. Brian Primack, director of the Center for Media,

Technology, and Health Research, states that mental health and social isolation have reached epidemic levels among youth. “By nature, we are social beings. However, modern life is pulling us apart instead of bringing us closer together. Social media seems to fill this communication gap, but research shows that it is not the solution people hope for,” says Primack.

In 2014, Primack and his colleagues surveyed 1,787 Americans aged 19-32 about their use of popular social networks. Using computer-based tests and psychological surveys, they measured respondents’ levels of social isolation. The findings revealed that teenagers who spend more than two hours a day on social media experience twice as much loneliness as their peers who spend less than 30 minutes online. Additionally, those who visit social media sites 58 times per week are three times more likely to feel lonely compared to those who check in only nine times per week. While it is premature to draw long-term conclusions about the harm of social media, researchers acknowledge that social media may either attract those who already feel lonely or contribute to real-life disconnection. “It is possible that initially lonely youth turn to social media for engagement, or that excessive use of social media leads to social withdrawal. A combination of both factors is also likely,” says Dr. Elizabeth Miller, a professor of pediatrics.

Scholars argue that social media consumes students’ free time, which could otherwise be spent interacting with real people, fostering personal development. Moreover, monitoring colleagues’ and friends’ lives through social media can lead to feelings of envy or dissatisfaction with one’s own life.

Youth represent the future of the nation and are key figures in building the New Uzbekistan. However, what do today’s young people spend most of their time on? The answer is clear—social media. The New Uzbekistan requires modern educators. In remote areas, some teachers struggle to use phones and computers, relying on students for assistance. Shouldn’t a modern teacher keep pace with technological advancements? A teacher cannot afford to make mistakes. Although they are human and prone to errors, they must always remember that their profession is the foundation of the nation's future.

Uzbek youth must love and protect their nation, develop a sense of gratitude and appreciation, and foster national consciousness—this is a crucial task today. While significant attention is given to education in our country, what about upbringing? Imagine the consequences of an “intelligent but ill-mannered” generation. As a future educator, I firmly believe that the solution to these issues lies in teachers occupying the digital space. The virtual world—websites and applications on social media—is the world of today's youth. These platforms are their closest "companions."

Is it correct? Teachers must and should be the closest people to students in the virtual world. Traditionally, our interaction with students only takes place in educational institutions. However, if our educators continue this interaction outside of class hours, we can quickly gain influence over the "children's world."

So, how can we achieve this? As you know, teachers work in various subject areas, such as language and literature, history, mathematics, biology, chemistry, and so on. Each skilled subject teacher should create a blog on social media related to their field. In these blogs, they should share interesting facts, problems, logical questions, solutions to challenges, and other subject-related information.

For example, let's take a mathematics teacher. They can highlight the role of mathematics in life, its essence, secrets, easy problem-solving techniques, and effective ways to learn mathematics faster. Other subject teachers should follow the same approach.

In conclusion, the person responsible for shaping students' digital literacy and culture in social networks is the teacher. We all know that the educator is the specialist who ensures continuous education and upbringing for future generations.

Pay attention—the word "pedagogue" itself means "one who leads a child," right? But what about the child? Who is the child following? I don't understand why our students should be following some ignorant and immoral "bloggers." Are our scholars and teachers really incapable of taking over social media? Do they lack the skills or resources for this?

If our teachers were to run blogs as skillfully as those so-called "bloggers," they would do it a thousand times better. If our educators take this approach, the status of teachers in our country will rise significantly, and people's perception of them will fundamentally change.

Why? Because talented teachers will begin to showcase their knowledge to a wider audience. As a result, every segment of our society will see firsthand what kind of person a true educator is, witnessing their intellectual potential and expertise. I firmly believe that this is the way to spark the younger generation's interest in science and help them develop much more rapidly.

Indeed, Uzbek youth have the ability to showcase their intellectual talents on the global scientific stage because they are exceptionally gifted compared to the youth of other nations. In our blood runs the legacy of not just a few, but countless encyclopedic scholars who have shaken the world with their scientific achievements. Awakening this inherent strength is now the responsibility of our teachers.

I confidently say—they can accomplish this!

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Tanqidiy tahlil, qat'iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik – har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik qoidasi bo‘lishi kerak. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2016 yil yakunlari va 2017 yil istiqbollari bag‘ishlangan majlisidagi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti nutqi. // Xalq so‘zi gazetasi, 2017.16 yanvar, №11
2. Axmedova M.E., Toshkentboyeva U.A., Suyunova E.SH.// “Umumiy pedagogika” Darslik // “Tibbiyot nashriyoti matbaa uyi” mchj Toshkent – 2022, 231 bet.
3. Axmedova M.E., va boshqa. Umumiy pedagogika nazariyasi va amliyoti. – T.: “Fan va texnologiya”, 2019, 296 bet
4. Ergashev E. A. Talaba yoshlar mediasavodxonligi-davr talabi. Инновации в педагогике и психологии. Т.: (2023). 6(3).